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Winter 12-5-2021

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Panda, Subhajit and Sinhababu, Dr. Atasi, "An Analysis of the Research Productivity & Research Interests of Library and Information Science Department of Panjab University in Zenodo Community" (2021).

Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal). 6707.

<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6707>

An Analysis of the Research Productivity & Research Interests of Library and Information Science Department of Panjab University in Zenodo Community

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Abstract:

The crisis in open access scholarly communications leads to several initiatives promoting the development of open access repositories. It reduces the repetition of research studies by minimising the cost of access and encouraging the reuse of research data. But at the same time, the contributor researchers are also concerned about the long term preservation, meta-descriptions and citation support of their research publication shard in open access repositories. Zenodo, as an open access repository, supports a wider variety of use cases, and many of them implement minimal control on the data uploaded by users. The present study discusses the research output & research interest of the Library and Information Science Department of Panjab University by collecting data from the Zenodo community. The analysis highlights yearly output of research publications, relative growth rate & doubling time, upload trends, authorship patterns, most productive authors, most preferred sources & source origins, length of the publications, used reference count & reference types and top used keywords. Researchers' research performance is demonstrated by calculating the views & downloads of a specific article in the community. The study also reveals the inadequacy of the Zenodo community in keeping track of contributors' citations. In conclusion, the study suggests following up some motivational & functional requirements to encourage researchers to contribute their works in open access repositories. In ethical consideration, it eliminates the digital divide, as well as maximising the societal benefits of research.

Keywords: Dataset repositories, Open access repositories, Department of Library and Information Science, Panjab University, Research productivity, Research output, Zenodo communities

1. Introduction:

The preservation and availability of research data is a serious challenge since it affects major scientific principles such as repeating and contrasting experiments and sharing results. This worry has resulted in several projects and services that provide long-term preservation of research data in general, with many of them exposing data and its descriptions in an open-access format. Zenodo is one of such initiatives with the key feature of offering mechanisms for the persistent identification and archiving of datasets together with services for sharing them and making them citeable. It is vital to know all of the facts to properly comprehend & recreate the existing researches. In the digital age, this includes digital artefacts, which are all accepted by Zenodo. Zenodo does not impose any format, size, access limitations, or licence requirements to be an effective catch-all that removes barriers to implementing data sharing

techniques and leave no excuse for researchers not to share their findings (Zenodo, 2013). As Zenodo does not restrict the creation of communities by registered users, their creation and functioning respond only to the will of individuals and communities engaged with the repository. It makes the Zenodo repository an intriguing example of a data curation repository in which researcher behaviour is manifested both in the repository's growth and actual use, as well as in community selection (Sicilia et al., 2017). In this study, the research output & research interests of the Library and Information Science Department of Panjab University in the Zenodo community were analysed using some bibliometrics parameters.

2. About Zenodo:

Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>) is a multi-disciplinary open access repository maintained by CERN. It was launched in 2013 and is part of OpenAIRE (Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe). The name “Zenodo” is derived from “Zenodotus”, the first librarian of the Ancient Library of Alexandria and father of the first recorded use of metadata, a landmark in library history (Zenodo, 2013). Scholars from any research discipline can upload data in any file format in the Zenodo repository. A digital object identifier (DOI) is automatically assigned to all Zenodo files. If an already published file (APF) has a DOI assigned by the publisher, the user can utilise that DOI when uploading the file; and Zenodo will not generate a new DOI for the file. All of the Zenodo Data is stored in CERN Data Center. Zenodo accepts up to 50 GB per dataset and there is no limit for the Zenodo community. Zenodo and the underlying Invenio Framework for digital repositories were designed according to the OAIS reference model along with the most recent ISO 16363 certification.

2.1. About the Zenodo Community:

Zenodo allows users to build communities in Zenodo. It helps to manage the research output of a particular author, a particular subject, a particular institution or a particular nation in a easy manageable and widely discoverable manner. The creator of the community can accept or reject uploads submitted to it, and can moderate it as per his/her own policy.

A community can be created by providing some basic information e.g.

- a) **Identifier:** The identifier is used in the URL for the community collection, and cannot be modified later.
- b) **Title:** Community Name
- c) **Description:** A short description of the community collection, which will be displayed on the index page of the community.
- d) **Curation Policy:** The policy by which a new upload is accepted/reject in this community.
- e) **Page:** A long description of the community collection, which will be displayed on a separate page linked from the index page.
- f) **Logo:** Image file used to aid and promote instant public recognition.

As a creator, a user can Curate the community’s collection by accept & reject a new upload, can export the collection automatically via OAI-PMH, and can get an custom upload link to send colleagues, fellow users or can attach it in the website of institutional repository or library website.

2.1.1. DLIS, PU, Chandigarh, India Community

Prof. Rupak Chakravarty created a community on February 6, 2018, namely, “**Department of Library & Information Science, Panjab University, Chandigarh, INDIA**” (available through, <https://zenodo.org/communities/dlispu/>), to curate the research works of persons affiliated with the Department of Library Science, Panjab University, Chandigarh. The description of this community

promotes the 'FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, published in 2016, intended to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets. The community covers the publications in which minimum one author affiliated from DLIS, PU.

3. Review of Literature:

The study aimed to analyse the research productivity of a particular university or institution using metrics studies is not a new area of research. Some important studies are mentioned here to help readers grasp this fundamental area.

Teli & Dutta (2008) attempted to analyze quantitatively the growth of research output in Vidyasagar University in terms of publication output as reflected in the web of science database over the years 1989 to 2014. The data was collected from the web of science database. The analysis highlighted yearly output of research publications, publishing trend, authorship pattern, funding agencies, collaborating organizations, collaborating countries, most productive authors of the University, most preferred journals for publication, citation profile of the contributed papers and the top-cited papers and authors of the University. It is observed that the analyzed results tally well with Bradford's distribution for bibliographic scattering and Lotka's law of author productivity. **Siwach & Satish Kumar (2015)** investigated the research contributions of Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak in terms of its publication output during 2000-2013 as reflected through the Scopus database. The study analyzed the year-wise research productivity, its citations impact, national and international collaborations, top collaborating institutions, subject-wise distribution of papers, journals used for communication, most preferred journals for publication, most prolific authors, number of citations received, and top-cited papers of the University during the period under study. The study of **Naqvi (2021)** was taken to analyse the research productivity of the University of Delhi during the last 30 years. The data for the analysis was downloaded from SCI and analysed with the help of MS Excel. The study findings suggested that, among the three hypotheses of the article, 'H₁: The growth rate of literature in these universities is steady since 1989' was neither approved nor disapproved, 'H₂: The journal article as source of publication occupies the top rank' was approved, 'H₃: English is highly preferred language used by the faculty to disseminate their research output' was approved. In a similar study, **Yadav & Sahu (2014)** depicted the research performance of the University College of Medical Science (UCMS) in different areas or subfields of medical and health sciences. This study was based on a bibliometric analysis of scientific research output collected from the SCOPUS database by using different searching techniques. Some bibliometric indicators such as authorship pattern, degree of collaboration, author productivity, rank distribution etc. have been used to illustrate the research performance of researchers. **Rawat et al. (2021)** aimed to examine the research productivity of the FRI, Dehradun, during 1990-2019. The data for the present study were collected from the Scopus database. VOS viewer with version 1.6.16 was adopted to visualize Co-authorship analysis, Co-occurrence analysis, and Co-citation analysis. Scientometrics indicators like author productivity, collaboration coefficient, modified collaboration coefficient, co-authorship index, etc were used. **Kabba & Ejbari (2021)** analyzed research productivity at Moroccan public universities. This study contributed to the rare literature that exists about African research productivity in general and research at Moroccan public universities especially. The study focused on the period 2008 to 2018, and used the most recent available data and used bibliometrics indicators to evaluate research at Moroccan public universities. **Sahoo et al. (2021)** investigated the trends of basic science research in India using a combination of qualitative and quantitative approaches. It examined the publication patterns and impact of research productivity of five basic science institutions, i.e., "Indian Institutes of Science Education and Research" (IISER), namely IISER Kolkata, IISER Pune, IISER Mohali, IISER Bhopal, and IISER Thiruvananthapuram indexed in the SCOPUS bibliographic database obtained from 2015 to 2019. A total number of 7329 research publications were analysed using various scientometric dimensions. The findings reveal that these institutions are accountable for important research outcomes, such as a high number of citations, preferences towards open access (OA) publications, a rise in research publication

year over year, a strong author network, a high degree of collaboration, and a high impact in terms of other scientometrics indicators. **Gupta et al. (2021)** aimed at analysing the research productivity of the University of Jammu for a period of ten years during 2010-2019. A total of 1641 papers were retrieved from Incites database during the covered period of 10 years. These papers were analysed using different bibliometric techniques for studying the research productivity in different parameters such as publication growth pattern, mode of publications, citation pattern, prolific authors, preferred journals, authorship pattern, collaboration pattern, etc. The results revealed that there is continuous growth in publication productivity, and most of the output is published in the form of journal articles.

The above studies included the research output of a single university based on the data derived from WoS, Scopus or other indexing databases and analysed according to some metrics parameters. The present study provides uniqueness by covering a new platform, the Zenodo community, to assess the research trends of a particular department of a university.

4. Research Objectives:

The major objectives of the present study are,

- (a) To examine year-wise growth of publications in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (b) To calculate the Relative Growth rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (D_t) of publications in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (c) To identify document upload trends in DLIS, PU community in Zenodo (Year-wise).
- (d) To highlight authorship pattern, degree of collaboration and top contributors of publications in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (e) To discover contributors' affiliation, designation & geographical distribution.
- (f) To evaluate document accessibility status of publications in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (g) To know the publication sources & origin of those publications sources in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (h) To ascertain average length of publication, use of references per article & types of cited references in the publications of DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.
- (i) To analyse the research interest of the publications of DLIS, PU community in Zenodo platform.
- (j) To identify the most used keywords & used keywords frequencies of the publications in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo.

5. Scope of the Study:

The present research tends to analyse the research output of the Library and Information Science Department of Panjab University indexed in the Zenodo community, "Department of Library & Information Science, Panjab University, Chandigarh, INDIA". The study was confined to Publication type "Article" in its initial line of data extraction to obtain intact data and better interpretation. Again, while gathering data, it was discovered that numerous research scholars and faculty members submitted documents to this community in which none of the author(s) had acquired the DLIS, PU designation & affiliation. Many of them are now working under DLIS, PU, but they were affiliated with another university at the time article was published. Similarly, instead of DLIS, PU, some working research scholars put their work institution & designation. For enhanced mapping, such publications are not considered under this study.

6. Research Methodology:

The data about the research publications collected from the community page of Zenodo manually , and then analysed with the help of Microsoft Excel software.

	Total Publications	Limited to Articles (Stage 1)	Remove Non Designated & Affiliated under PU, DLIS (Stage 2)	Remove wrongly mentioned Publication Types (Stage 3)
No. of Publications	85	70	62	59 (Final Sample)

Table 1: Selection of Target Sample Group

The data was retrieved from the targeted community, “Department of Library & Information Science, Panjab University, Chandigarh, INDIA” on 24 November 2021. Out of the 85 publications, after limiting the document type “Article” in the first stage, 70 publications remain. At Stage 2, with performing a systematic review, nearly eight (8) publications were excluded because DLIS, PU is not a designation & affiliation of a minimum one of the author(s). The third stage of screening removed three (3) publications because they were conference papers and uploaded under the “Article” document category. After going through all of the rigorous cleaning procedures, 59 articles were finalised as the target samples of the study (see Table 1).

Retrieving Date: 24 November 2021

Community: Department of Library & Information Science, Panjab University, Chandigarh, INDIA

Web Link: <https://zenodo.org/communities/dlispu/>

7. Data Analysis & Discussion:

After finalising the study sample and collection of the data, the collected data was categorized & explained according to some notable parameters viz. year-wise growth; relative growth rate & doubling time; upload trend in Zenodo repository; authorship pattern; degree of collaboration; top contributors; contributors’ affiliation, designation & origin; accessibility, source & source origin; page length; reference per document & types of reference cited; and research interests in Zenodo by evaluating downloads/unique downloads & views/unique views.

7.1. Year-wise Growth of Publication:

Figure 1: Year-wise Growth of Zenodo Uploads (according to publication date)

Figure 1 displays the year wise growth of publications indexed under DLIS, PU community of Zenodo. According to the stats, the highest no of uploads of the Zenodo community (13 or 22.03%) possesses the 2021 publication year, followed by 2018, 2017 & 2020 with 15.25% (9), 11.86% (7) & 11.86% (7) of total coverage respectively. It's important to note that, though the publication date of the uploaded contents starts from the year 2005, there are several years with zero publications, viz. 2006, 2007, 2008 & 2013.

7.2. Relative Growth rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (Dt):

According to Mahapatra (1985), the growth of publication (mainly year-wise) or the research output can be analysed by two interrelated parameter, Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (Dt). RGR is a measure to study the increase in the number of publications of time. It is calculated as,

$$RGR = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{T_2 - T_1}$$

Where,

P₂ and P₁ are the cumulative number of publications in the year's T₂ and T₁;

W₁= Log_eP₁ (Logarithm of initial number of publication);

W₂=Log_eP₂ (Logarithm of final number of publication).

The time necessary for publications to double their current volume is known as doubling time, which is directly related to the Relative Growth Rate (RGR). Again, if the number of articles in a subject doubles over time, the difference between beginning & end logarithms must be Log_e2 (value in napier logarithm = 0.693) (A. & Kannappanavar, 2020). So the Doubling time is calculated using the following formula:

$$Dt = \frac{0.693}{RGR}$$

Where,

D_t= Doubling time

RGR= Relative Growth Rate

Year	Publication	Cumulative Publication	W ₁ (lnP ₁)	W ₂ (lnP ₂)	RGR (W ₂ -W ₁)	Mean RGR	D _t	Mean D _t
2005	1	1	-	0.00		0.24		0.76
2006	0	1	0.00	0.00	0.00			
2007	0	1	0.00	0.00	0.00			
2008	0	1	0.00	0.00	0.00			
2009	1	2	0.00	0.69	0.69		1.00	
2010	1	3	0.69	1.10	0.41		1.69	
2011	2	5	1.10	1.61	0.51		1.36	
2012	2	7	1.61	1.95	0.34		2.04	
2013	0	7	1.95	1.95	0.00	0.24		2.51
2014	2	9	1.95	2.20	0.25		2.77	
2015	3	12	2.20	2.48	0.28		2.48	
2016	5	17	2.48	2.83	0.35		1.98	
2017	7	24	2.83	3.18	0.35		1.98	

2018	9	33	3.18	3.50	0.32		2.17	
2019	6	39	3.50	3.66	0.16		4.33	
2020	7	46	3.66	3.83	0.17		4.08	
2021	13	59	3.83	4.08	0.25		2.77	
Total	59	-	-	-	-	0.24	-	1.64

Table 2: Relative Growth Rate (RGR) and Doubling Time (D) of Research Output (2005-2021)

It is evident from Table 2 that the year 2009 obtained maximum relative growth rate (RGR) value (i.e. 0.69) while the year 2019 has the lowest RGR value (= 0.16). The average value of the RGR is 0.24, also indicated as Mean RGR. Similarly, in-opposite, the year 2009 has the least doubling time value (i.e. 1.00) while the year 2019 possess the highest doubling time value (i.e. 4.33). The mean value of the doubling time is 1.64. Table 2 also indicate that the value of RGR & D_t doesn't follow any fixed pattern of increasing or decreasing trend.

7.3. Upload Trend in Zenodo Repository:

Figure 2: Document Upload Trends in Zenodo Community (Year-wise)

Although the publication year of the uploaded documents of the DLIS, PU community in Zenodo ranges from 2005 to 2021; the documents uploaded in the community from its inception (i.e. 2018) to the current year (i.e. 2021). Figure 2 shows that in 2021, the DLIS, PU community has the highest number of uploads (49.15%) and the year 2019 with 26 uploads (44.07%) closely followed it (see Figure 2).

7.4. Authorship Pattern:

The precise authorship patterns of the uploaded articles in the DLIS, PU community are shown in Figure 3. Two authors contributed to 83% (or 49) of the 59 papers, followed by publications with one and three authors (4 or 7%). The input of 5 authors in a single article is the most in all of the community's publications.

Figure 3: Authorship Pattern of the Documents in DLIS, PU Community

7.5. Degree of Collaboration:

The 'Degree of Collaboration' is known as the ratio of the number of collaborative research papers to the total number of research papers in the discipline during a certain period of time (Subramanyam, 1983) and can be written as,

$$\text{Degree of Collaboration, DC} = \frac{N_M}{N_S + N_M}$$

Where,

DC = degree of collaboration

N_M = number of multiple-authored articles

N_S = number of single authored research articles.

	Single Author (N_S)	Multiple Author (N_M)	Total ($N_S + N_M$)	Degree of Collaboration [$DC = N_M / (N_S + N_M)$]
No. of Publications	4	55	59	0.93

Table 3: Degree of Collaboration

The degree of collaboration among the contributors is depicted in Table 3. It shows that 55 of the 59 articles are multi-authored publications, with only four (4) contributions from a single author. The overall degree of collaboration is calculated as 0.93.

7.6. Most Productive Contributors:

Rank	Author(s)	Count	Author(s) Position			
			1st	2nd	3rd	More
1	Rupak Chakravarty	45	16	26	1	2
2	Preeti Mahajan	10	3	7	0	0

3	Shivani Kaushal	9	9	0	0	0
4	Jyoti Sharma	9	4	4	0	1
5	Deepti Madaan	5	3	2	0	0
6	Khushpreet Singh Brar	4	3	1	0	0
7	Atasi Sinhababu	4	3	0	1	0
8	Nidhi Gupta	3	3	0	0	0
9	Surbhi Arora	3	2	1	0	0
10	Amandeep Kaur	3	0	0	3	0
11	Anil Kumar	2	2	0	0	0
12	Subhajit Panda	2	2	0	0	0
13	Diksha Diksha	2	1	1	0	0
14	Simran Kaur	2	1	1	0	0
15	Pooja Kumari	2	1	0	0	1
16	Bhupinder Singh	2	0	2	0	0
17	Shiv Kumar	2	0	2	0	0
18	Heenam Gakhar	2	0	1	1	0
Others (with single contribution)		13	6	7	0	0

Table 4: Top Contributors of DLIS, PU Community

It's indicated from Table 4 that out of the 31 different contributors of 59 publications understudy, almost 45 contributed by Rupak Chakravarty in various authorship positions. He is the most contributed author among all. With a contribution in 10 publications, Preeti Mahajan placed in the second position and Shivani Kaushal & Jyoti Sharma secured the third position with 9 publications each. In Table 4, while ranking between authors with the equal number of contributions, the position of the author (*first, second, third or more*) is taken under consideration.

7.7. Contributors' Affiliation:

In Table 5, the author's affiliation counts one (1) in each time they are featured in an article. Also, if an author uses two different affiliations in two separate publications, the overall count includes both affiliations. As a result, the affiliation count was clearly higher than the total number of publications and authors. Thus, to indicate the affiliation's contribution to the research output of the community, the percentage is better represented than their count.

SN	Contributors' Affiliation	Count	Percentage	Rank
1	Panjab University	103	83.06	1
2	Punjabi University	4	3.23	2
3	DAV College, Chandigarh	3	2.42	3
4	Central University of Punjab	2	1.61	4
5	Chandigarh University	2	1.61	4
6	Department cum Centre for Women Studies and Development, Panjab University	2	1.61	4
7	Goswami Ganesh Dutta Sanatam Dharma College	2	1.61	4
8	Chandigarh College of Engineering and	1	0.81	5

	Technology			
9	Divisional Library(South), Sector 34, Chandigarh	1	0.81	5
10	GGDSD College, Kheri Gurna, Banur	1	0.81	5
11	ShahzadaNand College	1	0.81	5
12	Swami Devi Dyal Institute of Engineering	1	0.81	5
13	Thapar University	1	0.81	5
Total		124	100.00	

Table 5: Affiliation of the Contributors of DLIS, PU Community

As the parent institution of the community, the contribution of “Panjab University” (83.06%) is far away from the rest. Among the rest, some universities like Punjabi University (3.23%) and DAV College (Chandigarh) (2.42%) contributed most to the community.

7.8. Contributors’ Designation:

Similar to previous Table 5, in Figure 4, the author's designation counts one (1) each time they are featured in an article. Also, if an author uses two different designations in two separate publications, the overall count includes both designations. As a result, the designation count was clearly higher than the total number of publications and authors. Thus, to indicate the designation-wise contribution to the research output of the community, the percentage is better represented than their count.

Figure 4: Designation of the Contributors of DLIS, PU Community

Figure 4 displays that majority of the contributors are Research Scholars (29%), followed by Professors (21%), Assistant Professors (15%) and Associate Professors (14%). Its is pleasant to see that there are 3% students among the contributors of the community.

7.9. Geographical Distribution of the Contributors:

As none of the contributors of the community has an collaboration with the foreign author outside India, the geographical distribution (country-wise) of the contributors limited to India only.

Figure 5: State of the Contributors of DLIS, PU Community

Moreover, Figure 5 displays the state-wise distribution of the contributors. According to stats on the figure, 90% of the contributors are from Chandigarh (UT), 9% from Punjab and 1% from Haryana. Also, only these three UT/states are contributed to the contributors' geographical origin.

7.10. Document Accessibility Status of Zenedo Community:

Figure 6: Document Accessibility Status of DLIS, PU Community

Figure 6 shows that in Zenodo's DLIS, PU community, there are three different sorts of accessible content. Out of the 59 articles, 81% (48) are openly accessible and 14% (8) are in closed access. Apart from these, 5% of publically accessible documents are either available in abstract versions or accessible only the author accepted manuscript (AAM) because they were published in a closed-access journal.

7.11. Source of Publication:

SN	Source	Count (n%)	Rank
1	Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)	22 (37.29%)	1
2	International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology	4 (6.78%)	2

3	International Journal of Information Studies & Libraries	3 (5.08%)	3
4	International Journal of Information, Library & Society	3 (5.085)	3
5	Journal of Indian Library Association	2 (3.39%)	4
6	Library Hi Tech News	2 (3.39%)	4
7	PEARL - A Journal of Library and Information Science	2 (3.39%)	4
8	The Diviner: A Research Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences	2 (3.39%)	4
9	Asia-Pacific Journal of Social Sciences	1 (1.69%)	5
10	Asian Journal of Library and Information Science	1 (1.69%)	5
11	DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology	1 (1.69%)	5
12	Gyankosh	1 (1.69%)	5
13	IASLIC Bulletin	1 (1.69%)	5
14	IFLA Journal	1 (1.69%)	5
15	International Journal of Digital Library Services	1 (1.69%)	5
16	International Journal of Information Movement	1 (1.69%)	5
17	International Journal of Information Research	1 (1.69%)	5
18	International Journal of Information Studies and Libraries	1 (1.69%)	5
19	International Journal of Knowledge Management and Practices	1 (1.69%)	5
20	Journal of Advanced Research in Library and Information Science	1 (1.69%)	5
21	Journal of Advancements in Library Sciences	1 (1.69%)	5
22	Journal of Advances in Library and Information Science	1 (1.69%)	5
23	Journal of Library and Information Science	1 (1.69%)	5
24	KIIT Journal of Library and Information Management	1 (1.69%)	5
25	Library Progress (International)	1 (1.69%)	5
26	Performance Measurement and Metrics	1 (1.69%)	5
27	SRELS Journal of Information Management	1 (1.69%)	5
Total		59 (100.00%)	

**Shaded journals are International Journals and the rest National Journals*

Table 6: Uploaded Documents Source of DLIS, PU Community

Table 6 lists the contributed sources of publishing arranged by productivity in descending order. All 59 publications in the DLIS, PU community were published from 27 different journals. The “Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)” published 22 (37.29 %) of the 59 articles, while the “International Journal of Information Dissemination and Technology” contributed 6.78% (4 articles). Apart from these, two journals each provided three articles, four journals each contributed two articles, and 19 journals each produced only one article.

7.12. Origin of Publication Source:

Figure 7: Origin of Publication Source

Among the 27 contributor journals (listed in Table 6), six (6) journals have International origin with a contribution of 47% (28) articles on the DLIS, PU community. The rest 51% (31) articles came from 21 different National journals.

7.13. Average Length of the Publications:

SN	Page Range	No. of Publication	Percentage
1	0-5	8	13.56
2	6-10	18	30.51
3	11-15	11	18.64
4	16-20	11	18.64
5	More than 20	11	18.64
Total		59	100.00

Table 7: Average Length of Articles in DLIS, PU Community

Table 7 shows the length of articles categorised into five categories: 0-5, 6-10, 11-15, 16-20 and more than 20 pages. It is observed that the maximum number of articles viz, 18 out of 59 (30.51%) published with 6-10 pages of length. It is followed by 11-15, 16-20 & more than 20 pages with a coverage of 11 (18.64%) articles each. Articles with 0-5 pages are the least common (8 or 13.56%). It is also important to note the article entitled, “Paid Open Access: A Comparative Study of Selected International Publishers”, authored by Rupak Chakravarty & Dimple Sharma and published in International Journal of Digital Library Services, has the maximum page length (i.e. 39) among all the articles in the community.

7.14. Use of References per Article:

SN	Reference Count	No. of Publication	Percentage
1	0-5	7	11.86
2	6-10	20	33.90
3	11-15	13	22.03

4	16-20	9	15.25
5	More than 20	10	16.95
Total		59	100.00

Table 8: Use of Reference per Article

Table 8 depicts the number of references used in published articles in the DLIS, PU community. It is very clear from the table that the maximum number of articles (20 or 33.90%) in the community consists of 6-10 references per article; followed by 13 articles (22.03%) with 11-15 references and 10 articles (16.95%) with more than 20 references. It is important to note that the article entitled “Virtual Reference Service: Understanding Trends through Review of Literature” by Atasi Sinhababu consists of a maximum of 48 references among all the articles in the community.

7.15. Types of Reference Cited in the Articles:

Figure 8: Cited Reference Types

Figure 8 presents the type of material used by authors while constructing their articles as a reference or background study. From the figure, it can be identified that journal articles are the most used references with more than half coverage percentage viz. 57% (or 493) and closely followed by online articles with 30% (257) coverage. Among the rest, conference papers, book/book chapters & other reference types referred 45 (5%), 31 (4%) & 23 (3%) times respectively.

7.16. Research Interest in Zenodo Platform:

Research interest denotes the acceptability & importance of published research to fellow researchers. It can be determined by various kinds of usage statistics, e.g. by citation analysis, by recommendation, by views & downloads count etc. In this study, the views & downloads stats of the uploaded articles in the DLIS, PU community are considered to determine the research interest of a particular article. Zenodo database primarily tracks two types of events, viz. visits to a record page & downloads of a file. And for both the events, visitor, visitor type, country & referrer are the second stage tracking parameters.

After thoroughly identifying the anonymised visitor ID, investigating the visitor's kind (e.g. human, machine, or robot), tracking the IP origin, and the referrer domain; Zenodo offers four sorts of usage stats: View, Downloads, Unique Views, and Unique Downloads.

7.16.1. Views & Unique Views

A view is a user (human or machine) visiting record to a document in Zenodo, it excludes double click, page refresh, and robots. It is considered a unique view when a user visits the same document one or more times inside an hour and within the same time-window.

7.16.2. Downloads & Unique Downloads

Similarly, when a user downloads content from a document, every single file counts as one download. And if the users download the same content inside an hour and within the same time-window, it is considered as one unique download.

Because the dates of upload for the 59 articles range from 2018 to 2021, per-day usage statistics would be more generic in determining a document's research interest. Table 9 shows the number of views, downloads, unique views, and unique downloads for each of the 59 target articles each day.

Table 9: Views & Downloads Stats of Uploaded Documents in Zenodo Community

Art. No.**	Day from Upload Date	Views	Views per day	Downloads	Downloads per day	Unique Views	Unique Views per day	Unique Downloads	Unique Downloads per day
1	10	14	1.40	10	1.00	12	1.20	9	0.90
2	51	16	0.31	13	0.25	16	0.31	12	0.24
3	76	14	0.18	7	0.09	11	0.14	7	0.09
4	106	16	0.15	2	0.02	13	0.12	2	0.02
5	108	14	0.13	10	0.09	12	0.11	8	0.07
6	110	11	0.10	10	0.09	10	0.09	8	0.07
7	148	49	0.33	39	0.26	37	0.25	36	0.24
8	171	55	0.32	34	0.20	45	0.26	27	0.16
9	196	19	0.10	11	0.06	18	0.09	10	0.05
10	197	22	0.11	11	0.06	17	0.09	11	0.06
11	199	17	0.09	9	0.05	15	0.08	8	0.04
12	200	20	0.10	10	0.05	16	0.08	8	0.04
13	200	12	0.06	12	0.06	11	0.06	12	0.06
14	200	16	0.08	16	0.08	11	0.06	10	0.05
15	200	9	0.05	6	0.03	9	0.05	6	0.03
16	201	10	0.05	22	0.11	8	0.04	20	0.10
17	201	19	0.09	9	0.04	15	0.07	6	0.03
18	201	11	0.05	3	0.01	11	0.05	3	0.01
19	201	15	0.07	8	0.04	13	0.06	8	0.04
20	201	12	0.06	11	0.05	8	0.04	8	0.04
21	201	14	0.07	10	0.05	14	0.07	10	0.05
22	202	13	0.06	23	0.11	12	0.06	23	0.11
23	202	16	0.08	29	0.14	14	0.07	28	0.14
24	202	16	0.08	11	0.05	12	0.06	8	0.04
25	202	18	0.09	12	0.06	16	0.08	11	0.05

26	202	18	0.09	8	0.04	12	0.06	5	0.02
27	206	19	0.09	11	0.05	17	0.08	10	0.05
28	206	41	0.20	25	0.12	32	0.16	20	0.10
29	346	20	0.06	53	0.15	17	0.05	46	0.13
30	376	52	0.14	98	0.26	45	0.12	90	0.24
31	419	124	0.30	39	0.09	118	0.28	35	0.08
32	432	12	0.03	15	0.03	11	0.03	13	0.03
33	777	52	0.07	34	0.04	49	0.06	27	0.03
34	794	31	0.04	21	0.03	30	0.04	18	0.02
35	924	28	0.03	18	0.02	21	0.02	14	0.02
36	936	19	0.02	388	0.41	19	0.02	366	0.39
37	959	31	0.03	32	0.03	27	0.03	30	0.03
38	976	20	0.02	12	0.01	20	0.02	12	0.01
39	976	27	0.03	23	0.02	26	0.03	22	0.02
40	1004	39	0.04	22	0.02	31	0.03	20	0.02
41	1004	21	0.02	14	0.01	17	0.02	14	0.01
42	1004	33	0.03	35	0.03	31	0.03	33	0.03
43	1004	21	0.02	15	0.01	19	0.02	15	0.01
44	1004	26	0.03	18	0.02	21	0.02	13	0.01
45	1004	33	0.03	51	0.05	31	0.03	48	0.05
46	1004	32	0.03	18	0.02	27	0.03	16	0.02
47	1004	23	0.02	16	0.02	22	0.02	15	0.01
48	1006	23	0.02	31	0.03	22	0.02	28	0.03
49	1006	24	0.02	18	0.02	22	0.02	14	0.01
50	1007	43	0.04	1	0.00	37	0.04	1	0.00
51	1007	19	0.02	0	0.00	19	0.02	0	0.00
52	1007	15	0.01	0	0.00	14	0.01	0	0.00
53	1007	18	0.02	3	0.00	17	0.02	3	0.00

54	1007	19	0.02	6	0.01	14	0.01	6	0.01
55	1007	11	0.01	2	0.00	10	0.01	2	0.00
56	1007	25	0.02	2	0.00	20	0.02	1	0.00
57	1007	24	0.02	0	0.00	20	0.02	0	0.00
58	1051	46	0.04	32	0.03	42	0.04	27	0.03
59	1257	30	0.02	21	0.02	25	0.02	19	0.02

*Shaded areas denotes top valued of that particular field

**Please discuss Appendix - I for the titles of the articles under study

According to Table 9, the article “STATUS OF OPEN ACCESS LIS JOURNALS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF DOAJ” authored by Rupak Chakravarty & Diksha Diksha has the maximum number of views (124) and unique views (118). Whereas, the article, “Virtual Reference Service: Understanding Trends through Review of Literature” authored by Atasi Sinhababu obtained the maximum number of downloads (388) and unique downloads (366). Although, if the per day average of the views, unique views, downloads & unique downloads calculated, the most recent upload “Assessing Q&A Trends in Scholarly Communications: a Quantitative Study of ResearchGate” beat all of the rest in the community.

7.17. Most Used Keywords in the Articles:

SN	Keywords	Count	Rank
1	E-Journals	10	1
2	Bibliographical Databases	9	2
3	E-Books	9	2
4	N-LIST	9	2
5	Degree Colleges of Panjab University	7	3
6	INFLIBNET	7	3
7	India	6	4
8	Library and Information Science	6	4
9	Chandigarh	5	5
10	Consortia	5	5
11	Open Access	5	5
12	Statistical Analysis	5	5
13	Usage of E-Resources	5	5
14	Panjab University	4	6
15	Bibliometric analysis	3	7
16	Digital Reference Service	3	7
17	DRS	3	7
18	Virtual Reference Service	3	7
19	VRS	3	7
20	Others (with frequency 2)	38	-
21	Others (with frequency 1)	182	-
Total Keywords Used (unique)		239	
Overall Keywords Used (with all freq.)		365	

Table 10: Most Used Keywords

Table 10 listed out most used keywords in the articles of DLIS, PU community. All of the 59 articles used a total of 365 keywords and out of them 239 unique ones. Out of the 239 unique keywords, E-Journals used the maximum times (with frequency 10), closely followed by Bibliographical Databases, E-Books & N-LIST (with frequency 9). The word clouds below also created by the used keywords and the size of a keyword in the cloud indicate its frequency.

Figure 9: Word Clouds

8. Major Findings of the Study:

The major findings of the study summarized as follows,

- 1) Among the 59 articles in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo, the year 2021 contributed with the most published (13 or 22.03%) as well as most uploaded (29 or 49.15%) articles in a single year term.
- 2) In between the publication range (i.e. 2005-2021) the mean RGR value is 0.24 while mean D_t value is 1.64.
- 3) Among the targeted articles 83% (or 49) published by two authors and the overall degree of collaboration is calculated as 0.93.
- 4) Among 31 different contributors of 59 publications understudy, almost 76.27% (45) contributed by Rupak Chakravarty in various authorship positions.
- 5) As the parent institution of the community, the contribution of “Panjab University” (103 or 83.06%) is far behind the rest, although lacking in inter-university collaboration.
- 6) The majority of the contributors are Research Scholars (29%) and belongs to Chandigarh (UT) (90%).
- 7) Out of the 59 articles in DLIS, PU community of Zenodo, 81% (48) are openly accessible in its original publishers version.
- 8) 51% of the articles in DLIS, PU community published in National journals while rest 47% in have International origin. Library Philosophy and Practices e-journal contributed most (37.29%) among all.
- 9) In DLIS, PU community of Zenodo, majority of the articles have 6-10 page length (30.51%) and used 6-10 references per article (33.90%) as well.
- 10) More than half of the cited references are journal articles (57%).
- 11) The article “Status of Open Access LIS Journals: An Empirical Study of DOAJ” by Rupak Chakravarty & Diksha has the maximum number of views (124) and unique views (118). Whereas, the article, “Virtual Reference Service: Understanding Trends through Review of Literature” by Atasi Sinhababu obtained the maximum number of downloads (388) and unique downloads (366).
 - a) In the per day average of the views, unique views, downloads & unique downloads, the most recent upload “Assessing Q&A Trends in Scholarly Communications: a Quantitative Study of ResearchGate” beat all of the rest in the community.
- 12) Out of the 239 unique keywords used in 59 articles, E-Journals used the maximum times (with frequency 10), closely followed by Bibliographical Databases, E-Books & N-LIST (with frequency 9).

9. Study Limitations:

Despite the provision of tracking citations of submitted documents in Zenodo, all 59 targeted documents display zero (0) citations in DLIS, PU community. This is a major shortcoming of the study. If the Zenodo help forum referred, this is primarily due to,

- The record has not yet been cited.
- The citations to the record have not yet been discovered by any of the Zenodo’s citation data sources.
- The domain of the record is not covered by any of the Zenodo’s citation data sources.
- The citations are not freely available.

Further investigation reveals that many of the targeted articles have been cited multiple times in the Scopus and Google Scholar databases and are freely available. As a result, the first and last points are invalid. The cause for untraceable citations is due to the limitations of Zenodo's citation data sources in terms of number and coverage. As of January 2019, Zenodo currently receives citation data from two sources:

- NASA Astrophysics Data System (astronomy and astrophysics).
- DataCite and Crossref Event Data (cross-domain)

10. Conclusion:

One of the foundations of the open research paradigm is open research data repositories, enabling collaboration, interoperability, large-scale sharing and reuse. Various universities and third-party online platforms have started to develop diverse data repositories and digital research environments to allow researchers to share their resources and raw data sets without restrictions. Besides Zenodo, the university cloud service Sciebo, Harvard Dataverse and the Open Science Framework are noteworthy examples. Even though technological advancements have enabled researchers to share their work on open access platforms, there is a lack of adaption across the board. In their study, Zuiderwijk et al. (2020) systematically reviewed 32 open data studies (range: 2004 and 2019) and elicited drivers plus inhibitors for both open research data sharing and use in eleven categories total that are: 'the researcher's background', 'requirements and formal obligations', 'personal drivers and intrinsic motivations', 'facilitating conditions', 'trust', 'expected performance', 'social influence and affiliation', 'effort', 'the researcher's experience and skills', 'legislation and regulation', and 'data characteristics.' All open access repositories should enhance their understanding of these factors to reassure researchers about the safety of their research. Like in Zenodo, although open access articles and datasets are preferred, closed and restricted access items are still permitted. Furthermore, for each dataset uploaded to Zenodo, create a DOI identifier (if not exist already) that certifies the stable identity of the dataset. In addition to trustworthiness, improvement in citation tracking, broadening the source of citations, author profile, advanced search facilities, and advancement in data export system are some future suggestions to make Zenodo a more appealing open access repository and widely accepted among scholars.

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APPENDIX - I

Art. No.	Title	Art. No.	Title
1	Assessing Q&A Trends in Scholarly Communications: a Quantitative Study of ResearchGate	11	E-Governance Initiatives in India with Special Reference to Punjab
2	Science Mapping Analysis of Digital Humanities research: A scientometric study	12	Use of E-Journals by Library and Information Science Researchers of India: An Empirical Analysis
3	Science Mapping and Visualization of Research Data Management (RDM): Bibliometric and Scientometric Study	13	Role of Libraries in Facilitating Reading Habits: Use of All Inclusive Assistive Technologies
4	Research Publications on SARS-CoV-2 (COVID-19): A Study of Publication Trends using the R Package	14	Application of Lotka's Law in Library Science Literature of Select Central Universities in North India
5	Google Scholar Adoption by LIS Educators in India: An Exploratory Study	15	Information seeking behaviour of journalists in north India
6	Measuring Patent-Citations of LIS Literature: An analytical study of the Journal Scientometrics	16	Collection and Services in Children's Section of the Public Libraries in Chandigarh
7	Analytics for Measuring Library Use and Satisfaction of Mobile Apps	17	AWARENESS AND USE OF N-LIST E-RESOURCES OF THE SELECT DEGREE COLLEGES AFFILIATED TO PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH; A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS
8	Preserving Global Research Data: Role and Status of Re3data in RDM	18	Use of Library and Library Resources in University Libraries of Northern India: A Comparative Study between Research Scholars and Faculty Members
9	Library Performance Assessment of Service Quality through LibQUAL: The Case of Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU), Rohtak (India)	19	Library Performance Assessment of Service Quality through LibQUAL: The Case of Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU), Rohtak (India)
10	Strength Weakness Opportunity and Challenge (SWOC) of Collaborative Virtual Reference Service (VRS): A feasibility study in consortia environment	20	Library and Information Services of A.C. Joshi Libraries during COVID – 19 pandemic: a study of faculty satisfaction
21	School Libraries in India: Present-day Scenario	31	STATUS OF OPEN ACCESS LIS JOURNALS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF DOAJ
22	DESIGNING AND DEVELOPING BIOPHYSICS LIBRARY WEBSITES: A PRACTICAL APPROACH USING WEB 2.0 SERVICE	32	Factors influencing Higher Similarity and Plagiarism amongst Research Scholars: a Comparative Case Study of two Indian Universities- Centers of Higher Education
23	Mapping Library and Information Science Research Output: A Bibliometric Study of Panjab University, Chandigarh	33	Role of Library in Research Support: a Study of Bharathiar University
24	The pandemic of COVID 19 and Role of Academic Libraries	34	Library and Information Science Courses in India: Issues and Suggestions

25	Trends in IoT Research: A Bibliometric and Science mapping Analysis of Internet of Things	35	Awareness and Acceptance of E-Journals Among Researchers of LIS: An Empirical Analysis
26	Librarians' Perception Towards Virtual Reference Service (VRS): Innovation and Knowledge Cluster Use Case	36	Virtual Reference Service: Understanding Trends through Review of Literature
27	Making research data discoverable: an outreach activity of datacite	37	Paid Open Access: A Comparative Study of Selected International Publishers
28	Libre Open Access in Science Journals: An Analytical Study of DOAJ	38	Use of Internet by the Faculty Members & Students: A Case Study of Swami Devi Dyal Institute of Engineering
29	Preserving traditional knowledge: Initiatives in India	39	Webometric Analysis of Library Websites of Higher Educational Institutes (HEIs) of India: A Study through Google Search Engine
30	Evaluating the Web Accessibility of IIT Libraries: A Study of Web Content Accessibility Guidelines	40	USAGE OF N-LIST E-RESOURCES OF THE SELECT DEGREE COLLEGES AFFILIATED TO PANJAB UNIVERSITY, CHANDIGARH; A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS
41	Usage Trends of External Storage Media in N-List E-Resources by Select Degree Colleges Affiliated to Panjab University, Chandigarh: A Comparative Analysis	51	SCOPUS reflected study of selected research and higher education institutions (HEIs) of Chandigarh: a city of education and research
42	Identifying Problems and Suggestions for Improving the Services N-LIST E-Resources for Better Academic Pursuits	52	E-learning in Higher Education: Major Initiatives of Govt. of India
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